

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report presents projections of changes in global and regional marine primary productivity, with a particular focus on the Canary Current Upwelling System and its implications for West African fisheries. It utilises storm-resolving Earth System Model (SR-ESM) simulations and AI-based reconstructions to assess ecological trends and inform adaptive fisheries management in the context of climate change.

Work package in charge:

WP7

Lead author:

Patrice, André, Jean-Paul, Brehmer (IRD, Partner 22)

Other contributing authors:

Noel Keenlyside (UiB), Shunya Koseki (UiB), Elodie Martinez (IRD), Hervé Demarcq (IRD), Etienne Pauthenet (IRD), Thomas Gorgues (IRD), Keerthi Madhavan-Girijakumari (IRD), Ndague Diogoul (IRD), Aldo Affenou (IRD/UCAD), Yoba Kande (IRD/UADB), Saliou Faye (ISRA), Ndague Diogoul (ISRA), Abdoulaye Sarré (ISRA).

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Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Johann Jungclaus

2nd reviewer: Marcus Dengler

Contacts: Patrice.Brehmer@ird.fr & Noel.Keenlyside@uib.no

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Executive summary

Observations indicate a significant sea surface temperature (SST) warming off the northwest African coast (1995-2015), the highest worldwide for the tropical belt. This warming has led to a redistribution of key fish stocks along the coast, posing a risk to food security. An original statistical analysis using Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), built on 20 years of biological acoustic data, was then developed for small pelagic fish schools and micronekton to identify key environmental data that induce changes in their spatial distribution and relative biomasses. All significant GAMs combining SST, upwelling index and Sea surface Chlorophyll-*a* concentration (SSC) were considered.

Superimposed on the long-term warming, we show that part of the year-to-year variability gives rise to Dakar Niños. We demonstrate these impacts on SSC (here used as a proxy of primary productivity) and show that the nextGEMS model (hereafter referred to as IFS-FESOM) can adequately reproduce key features, such as interannual variability. The latitudinal pattern of the warm SST is correctly reproduced, which is attributed to the realistically resolved Senegal-Mauritania upwelling and Frontal Zone by IFS-FESOM. This is a notable strength of the IFS-FESOM compared to CMIP6 and High-ResMIP models, which have difficulties in resolving coastal upwelling.

A key aspect was to develop approaches based on IFS-FESOM simulations, which were primarily limited to physical parameters, in order to assess the benefits of resolving finescale dynamics and predicting future changes in marine ecosystems. We first developed a machine learning approach, based on UNet architecture, to predict SSC from physical parameters, including SST, sea surface salinity, and sea surface height. The model was trained and validated using observational and reanalysis data for independent periods.

At the global scale, SSC is projected by most climate models to remain relatively stable through mid-century, though with a wide spread, from weak declines to slight increases, impeding their robustness. IFS-FESOM-based SSC reconstruction shows a near-zero trend and low interannual variability. Yet, IFS-FESOM also provides enhanced spatial resolution in coastal and frontal zones, capturing biologically meaningful patterns that are often missed in coarse-resolution models.

In the West African region, model projections of SSC showed greater spatial complexity and variability than from large-scale trends. The IFS-FESOM-based SSC reconstruction indicates a near-zero trend in spatially averaged productivity through 2050, aligning with the majority of CMIP6 models, despite a wide inter-model spread. However, the spatial patterns differ significantly: IFS-FESOM projects localised increases in SSC along the coast, particularly in upwelling zones, while CMIP6 models display a wide range of trends. Even if there is no evidence that patterns from IFS-FESOM are more robust in terms of future SSC trends, this highlights the added value of storm-resolving models in capturing fine-scale processes essential to understanding regional ecosystem responses.

Projections based on IFS-FESOM simulations suggest limited changes in biological features across the West African upwelling system by mid-century, despite a high level of uncertainty. Our model-based forecast for *Sardinella aurita* (a small pelagic fish of key socioeconomic importance in West Africa) does not reproduce the northward shift observed over the past two decades, reflecting a divergence between recent historical trends and longer-term climate projections; nevertheless, the projected northern limit of the stock by 2050 remains consistent with recent observations. For fish school biomass, the key target of fisheries, simulations revealed strong sensitivity to environmental drivers, particularly Ekman transport and SSC, and a dramatic decrease, which could be due to a lack of ecosystemic consideration in our approach. Regarding micronekton, the IFS-FESOM-based projections indicate a slight reduction trend in biomass, but with high uncertainty due to limitations in resolving complex trophic and physical processes. These results illustrate both the potential and the current limits of using storm-resolving climate models for forecasting biological responses in complex coastal ecosystems. Nonetheless, IFS-FESOM performs better than CMIP6/HighResMip in reproducing the SST

front along NW Africa and associated extreme warming events, showing the evident benefit of high resolution. Nonetheless, IFS-FESOM performs better than CMIP6/HighResMIP in reproducing the SST front along NW Africa and associated extreme warming events, showing the evident benefit of high resolution. Additionally, the deliverable extends beyond its original scope by incorporating a complementary evaluation using the ICON-O/HAMOCC coupled model, which includes ocean biogeochemistry. This work has revealed that a realistic fine-scale spatial pattern emerges in Northwest Africa from the ICON-O/HAMOCC global simulation (10 km) within the complex Canary East border Upwelling system.

While nextGEMS models do not directly include biogeochemistry modules, they enable SSC reconstruction via deep learning approaches using physical drivers. This is a new capability that is currently out of reach for most CMIP6 outputs due to spatiotemporal mismatches and limited spatial and temporal resolution. These results illustrate the potential and also some current limitations of using storm-resolving climate models for forecasting biological responses in complex coastal ecosystems. This deliverable has enabled the development of a forecasting framework specifically suitable for West Africa, a data-poor region where such predictive tools remain scarce.

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Objectives and synergies

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics. The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with yes.

Specific objectives of the project: Contribution of this deliverable?

O1

To develop two SR-ESMs for applications

(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	Yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	No
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	Yes

O2

To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:

(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feed-backs;	No
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing; Specific objectives of the project Contribution of this deliverable?	No
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	Yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	No
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	Yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	No

Build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|---|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | No |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (<i>i.e.</i> , events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | Yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to achieving the specific objectives outlined in the Work Package description, as indicated below.

Objectives of WP7 Relevance in this deliverable?

- | | |
|--|-----|
| To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming (O1, O2) | No |
| To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming (O1, O2) | No |
| To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming. (O2) | No |
| To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs (O1, O2, O3) | Yes |
| To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments (O1, O2, O3) | No |
| To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system (O1) | No |

Synergies

A collaboration was developed with Dr Fatemeh Chegini and Prof Tatiana Ilyina, University of Hamburg, “Modeling the carbon cycle in the Earth system”. They provided unique data from a km-scale ICON Ocean/HAMOCC model simulation driven with atmospheric reanalysis. These data were used to analyse variability along the West African coast from 1997 to 2022. The data were produced under two projects, *i.e.*, ESM2025 and CLICCS. ESM2025 is funded by the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement 101003536: project ESM2025–Earth System Models for the Future; CLICCS is DFG-funded under Germany Excellence Strategy –EXC 2037 ‘CLICCS - Climate, Climatic Change, and Society’ (Project Number: 390683824).

We are working in synergy with the ANR-funded DREAM project (Deep Learning Approaches to Elucidate phytoplankton Climate-induced variability), coordinated by Elodie Martinez (University of Brest) and running from March 2023 to 2027 (400 k€). Collaboration will be extended beyond nextGEMS (2025-2027). DREAM leverages satellite and in situ data, combined with deep learning, to reconstruct and analyse multi-decadal variability in phytoplankton biomass and communities in response to climate forcing. By utilising nextGEMS outputs, our collaboration enhances ongoing efforts to assess the impacts of climate change on marine productivity at both the global scale and in the North-West Africa marine ecosystem. DREAM also brings continuity beyond the end of nextGEMS (2025), providing a framework to extend and deepen this work through to 2027.

The statistical analysis of the nextGEMS results presented in this deliverable will be enhanced through two groups. First, within FANE-MATH-PE¹, CNRS launches a new Joint Research Programme in mathematics to foster cooperation in Africa. FANE-MATH-PE aims to develop cutting-edge, applied mathematical tools for addressing critical global challenges, including climate change and ocean resource management. This long-term project aims to establish a sustainable, diverse network of researchers from France, Africa, and beyond, uniting young talents and seasoned experts, including men and women, in the field of applied mathematics. With a strong interdisciplinary focus, FANE-MATH-PE brings together specialists in applied mathematics, physics, biology, and biotechnology. It involves key French institutions (CNRS, IRD, INSERM, University of Lille) and several prominent African institutions (NRF, NWU -South Africa; UCAD, UGB, UADB -Senegal; Abomey Calavi-IMSP -Benin; Arba Minch University -Ethiopia; San-Pedro-Ivory Coast; AIMS centres). The project addresses pressing global issues, including climate change and overfishing. Initial efforts will involve designing models to address these challenges, which aim to improve the results of D7.3. A core research objective is to propose new mathematical, numerical, statistical, and AI (Artificial Intelligence) models and algorithms that combine accuracy, adaptability, and optimised computation times. These models will be rigorously tested for scalability and convergence under non-restrictive conditions and benchmarked against existing literature. Second, a workshop proposal was submitted in June 2025 to the ICMS Mathematics for Humanity Research Workshop grant. The title is “From Data to Impact: Advancing Climate Resilience in Africa through Statistics and Mathematical Modelling” which should be held in October 2026 at ICMS, Edinburgh (number of participants: 40) by Pr. Michelle Carey (University College Dublin, Statistics) and where nextGEMS output used in D7.3 will be further analysed (as one of the three identified data set).

This D7.3 work also supports the redaction of the new Strategic Plan of the Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission (SRFC) for 2025–2030, which will, for the first time, explicitly integrate the impacts of climate change into fisheries governance for the seven member states of the SRFC. In line with nextGEMS objectives, it contributes to tailoring SR-ESM outputs for fisheries management purposes, thereby bypassing traditional value-chain modelling to inform policy and decision-making at the sub-regional level directly. In parallel, a tripartite Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is being finalized between the Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission (SRFC), the University of Bergen (UiB), and the French

¹ <https://www.insmi.cnrs.fr/en/cnrsinfo/cnrs-africa-cooperation-launch-new-joint-research-programme-mathematics>

National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD). This Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) aims to formalise scientific cooperation in the field of climate change impacts and forecasting within the SRFC sub-region. It establishes a collaborative framework for joint research, capacity building, and shared use of outputs from CMIP6 and storm-resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESMs), including nextGEMS, to inform fisheries management and sub-regional planning. This agreement further strengthens the institutional uptake of the scientific work presented in this deliverable and ensures its long-term relevance for policy.

An ongoing project with the German Cooperation Service in Mauritania (15,000 k€; KfW Entwicklungsbank) "Promoting Sustainable Management of Fisheries Resources" (BMZ No. 2016 672 78, KfW Inpro No. 36029), implemented with German cooperation and COFAD, has identified climate change as one of six priority research themes for the national fisheries research institute, IMROP. This priority was confirmed in the 2024 "*Current State of Research at IMROP*" report (Labrosse et al., 2024), in which the term "climate change" appears over 70 times, underscoring its centrality. The project will now support several high-impact national research projects (~600 k€ each), including one specifically focused on climate change, which will leverage outputs from storm-resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESMs). This national initiative further reinforces the regional relevance of the work conducted under nextGEMS WP7 and its value for long-term climate-resilient fisheries planning.

A promising synergy is emerging through participation in the upcoming *TropEcs Symposium* (ZMT, Bremen, 22–25 September 2025), which will gather international experts in Earth System Modelling (ESM) to explore how tropical coastal ecosystems can be better represented in coupled climate models. This initiative, hosted by Prof. Dr. Raimund Bleischwitz, aims to identify key ecological and socio-environmental processes relevant to coastal regions and to define new modelling strategies integrating biosphere–atmosphere–human interactions (Catalyst Talk: Bjorn Stevens (Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, Germany), PI of nextGEMS). The symposium offers an ideal platform to present results from nextGEMS—including those developed under D7.3—and to establish collaborations that will help extend and valorise the scientific work achieved so far. It also provides a strategic opportunity to bridge the current advances in SR-ESM applications for fisheries with broader Earth system science agendas relevant to the Global South.

1. Introduction

Marine ecosystems are under growing pressure from climate change (Hoegh-Guldberg & Bruno, 2010; Poloczanska *et al.*, 2013), with implications for global primary productivity (Laufkötter *et al.*, 2015), biogeochemical cycles (Henson *et al.*, 2016), and the sustainability of fisheries (Chavez *et al.*, 2011; Blanchard *et al.*, 2012); especially in vulnerable regions such as northwest Africa (Brehmer *et al.*, 2018; Sarré *et al.*, 2024). Current Earth System Models (ESMs), while useful for global-scale climate projections, lack the spatial resolution necessary to accurately simulate fine-scale ocean processes (Bonan & Doney *et al.*, 2018) such as coastal upwelling (Sylla *et al.*, 2022), mesoscale dynamics (Hewitt *et al.*, 2020), and nutrient transport (Lévy *et al.*, 2024). These processes, however, are critical drivers of marine productivity and fisheries yields. The nextGEMS project addresses this limitation through the development and application of Storm-Resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESMs) that explicitly resolve key oceanic and atmospheric processes at kilometric scales (Segura *et al.*, 2025; see nextGEMS WP7). This deliverable contributes to assessing how climate change may affect global and sub-regional marine productivity, using a north-west African case study and nextGEMS simulations, along with associated model outputs. It also examines how these high-resolution simulations can be utilized to inform fisheries management in north-west Africa, which is home to some of the world's most productive and climate-sensitive upwelling systems.

Through a combination of model analysis, remote sensing data (coupling satellite and fisheries acoustics), and machine learning techniques, we aim to reconstruct and project changes in sea surface chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (hereafter referred to as SSC, *i.e.*, a proxy for marine productivity) and examine their implications for exploited fish populations. Special attention is given to the southern part of the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem, where changes in physical and biogeochemical conditions (Auger *et al.*, 2016) have a direct impact on sub-regional food security and economies (Thiaw *et al.*, 2017; Ba *et al.*, 2019; Baldé *et al.*, 2019). This work is carried out in collaboration with sub-regional scientific institutions and stakeholders to develop tools and knowledge to support adaptive, ecosystem-based fisheries management in the context of climate change.

This deliverable directly addresses the dual objectives of D7.3: (i) to project changes in global SSC and (ii) to assess their impact on West African fisheries. By leveraging nextGEMS simulations (capable of resolving fine-scale oceanic processes), we reconstruct present and future SSC, globally and regionally. The use of advanced deep learning techniques enables us to infer biologically meaningful patterns from physical variables, including SST, currents, and sea level anomalies. These reconstructions are validated using satellite data and then applied to the North-West African upwelling system to quantify ecological trends relevant to some key exploited fish stocks. In parallel, observed shifts in species *Sardinella aurita* are analyzed. The work thus provides a scalable framework for using storm-resolving ESMs to inform SSC assessments and to guide adaptive fisheries management in climate-vulnerable regions.

2. Models and data

This work relies on high-resolution simulations from the nextGEMS project, specifically utilising the coupled atmosphere–ocean IFS-FESOM model and, for complementary analysis, the ocean-only ICON-O model coupled with the HAMOCC biogeochemical model. For the IFS-FESOM simulations, two production cycles were used: (i) Cycle 2 (C2): a historical configuration run under fixed 2020 forcing, primarily used for validation and AI training. (ii) Cycle 4 (C4): a scenario run using SSP3-7.0 forcing for the period 2020–2050, enabling projections of marine ecosystem indicators under continued climate change. To reconstruct Sea Surface Chlorophyll-*a* Concentration (SSC), we developed a deep-learning approach (UNet architecture) trained on satellite observations (MODIS Aqua, 2003–2019) and physical predictors (sea surface temperature, sea surface height, eddy kinetic energy, and wind stress) extracted from the nextGEMS IFS-FESOM simulations. This approach allowed us to generate temporally continuous and spatially resolved reconstructions of SSC over the whole simulation period, capturing seasonal to multi-decadal signals.

In addition to IFS-FESOM, we incorporated a one-off simulation using ICON-O, coupled with HAMOCC, an ocean-only configuration that includes interactive biogeochemistry. This simulation, driven by atmospheric reanalysis, provided a complementary view of productivity and nutrient patterns along the Northwest African coast. We chose not to use the ICON Cycle 4 coupled simulation in this work, primarily because it covers only the future period and was not yet fully integrated into the ecological storyline at the time of analysis. Time constraints also prevented a parallel implementation of both model chains. For detailed documentation of model configurations and spatial domains, please refer to the nextGEMS online platform², which consolidates information on high-resolution climate simulations produced by the nextGEMS project and other European initiatives, such as the easy.gems platform³.

To link environmental change to ecosystem impacts, we also integrated biological and acoustic data from annual sea surveys conducted off Mauritania and Senegal between 1995 and 2015, with additional campaigns in 2011 and 2015. These surveys were conducted using the R/V Dr. Fridtjof Nansen, employing multifrequency echosounders and scientific trawl sampling (Project EAF-Nansen; FAO-Norad, IMR). We also used data from R/V Thalassa in 2014 (Project AWA; IRD-BMBF, 10.17600/14001400). The data were used to characterise historical environmental variability and species distribution shifts, to model the relationships between fish school density, micronekton biomass, and environmental drivers, and to analyse the northward shift of *Sardinella aurita*. These data provide critical ground truth for interpreting simulation-based projections and help bridge the gap between physical changes and biological responses.

Last, to constrain, train, and evaluate models, we used multiple satellite-based Earth observation products. These products were critical not only for training the deep learning model to reconstruct Sea Surface Chlorophyll-*a* (SSC), but also for extracting essential environmental variables used in the Generalised Additive Models (GAMs) that describe fish school dynamics and micronekton biomass. Specifically, we used (i) MODIS Aqua and OC-CCI for chlorophyll-*a* concentration (SSC). (ii) Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) Pathfinder v5.3 and Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) provided long-term records of sea surface temperature (SST). (iii) Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform wind product (CCMP) delivered consistent data on wind speed and wind stress. (iv) Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service “CMEMS” (Global Ocean Reanalysis and Simulation “GLORYS”) outputs were used for sea surface height (SSH) and eddy kinetic energy (EKE). These satellite-derived variables were harmonised and processed to match the temporal and spatial resolution required for both AI-based SSC reconstructions and/or GAM-based ecological modelling. The upwelling index is computed as the cross-shore Transport (Bakun 1973) as detailed in Sarré *et al.* (2024), from the CCMP Multi-Platform wind product⁴.

3. Effect of environmental variability and climate change on the north-west African east border upwelling system

This section is based on our work, both within and before nextGEMS. We employ a narrative style to simplify the deliverable, referring to key papers that already acknowledge nextGEMS, such as Sarré *et al.* (2024), Diogoul *et al.* (2024), and Kande *et al.* (2024). To gain a broader understanding of the impact of climate change on Northwest Africa, we invite the reader to review the nextGEMS deliverable 10.2.

3.1. Observed environmental variability and implications for zooplanktonic layers and small pelagic fisheries in NW Africa

Several studies have shown that fluctuations in sea surface temperature (SST), upwelling intensity, wind-driven turbulence, and large-scale climate indices such as the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO) are closely linked to the seasonal and interannual

² <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/introducing-easy-gems-your-gateway-to-next-generation-climate-modelling/>

³ <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/simulations/index.html>

⁴ <https://www.remss.com/measurements/ccmp/>

variability in the abundance and distribution of key small pelagic fish species, notably *Sardinella aurita* and *Sardinella maderensis* (Diankha *et al.*, 2015; Thiaw *et al.*, 2017; Baldé *et al.*, 2022). These species, which represent the bulk of artisanal fisheries landings in Senegal and Mauritania (Ba *et al.*, 2016; Baldé *et al.*, 2019; Ball *et al.*, 2024), exhibit distinct responses to environmental cues: *S. aurita* recruitment and migration are particularly sensitive to upwelling dynamics and SST variability, while *S. maderensis* appears more tolerant of thermal fluctuations but displays more localised spawning patterns.

Acoustic backscatter data from research vessels, along with satellite-derived ocean measurements, have also highlighted the importance of micronekton and zooplankton relative biomass (Diogoul *et al.*, 2021), mainly copepods, as a key trophic link supporting small pelagic fish. Using multifrequency echosounders and bi-frequency acoustic inversion methods, we have revealed high copepod biomass in the southern Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem (CCLME) (Diogoul *et al.*, 2024). These findings highlight the important role of lower trophic levels in driving fish productivity and underscore the vulnerability of the sub-regional food web to shifts in oceanographic regimes.

Diogoul *et al.* (2020) provided insights into the structure and dynamics of sound-scattering layers (SSLs) in the Senegalese upwelling region. A Generalized Additive Model (GAM) was developed to predict SSL vertical distribution and thickness in relation to temperature, salinity, oxygen, and density gradients. Their results demonstrated the key role of vertical environmental structure in shaping the distribution of mid-trophic layers, particularly zooplankton and micronekton, which are critical prey for small pelagic fish. By establishing quantitative links between physical conditions and the formation of Sound Scattering Layers (SSLs), this study provides a valuable framework for assessing how environmental variability—driven by climate change—can cascade through the food web and impact the behaviour and availability of pelagic fish in coastal ecosystems. Using spatial-functional statistical analysis, we have highlighted the importance of capturing fine-scale environmental variability to understand trophic dynamics in the CCLME. With Kande *et al.* (2024), we have demonstrated that variations in temperature and salinity at high spatial resolution have a significant impact on the structure and distribution of SSLs, which reflect zooplankton biomass. Using multifrequency acoustics and advanced modelling, the study showed that even subtle spatial gradients in hydrographic parameters can drive distinct patterns of micronekton and zooplankton layering, with implications for energy transfer to higher trophic levels. These findings reinforce the need for climate models capable of resolving sub-mesoscale ocean dynamics, particularly in upwelling regions where ecosystem productivity is tightly coupled to physical variability.

Understanding the sensitivity of zooplankton layers to fine-scale environmental variability reinforces the need for models that can project changes in the structure and dynamics of this key mid-trophic level. Such projections are essential for anticipating cascading effects on higher trophic levels, particularly exploited small pelagic fish, as further explored in Section 4.3.

3.2. Observed effects of climate change in North West Africa

The following synthesis of observed hydro-climatic and ecological trends in Northwest Africa provides not only a baseline for assessing the realism of nextGEMS high-resolution projections, but also the empirical basis for the statistical models (GAMs) developed later in this report to explore climate-driven changes in ecosystem structure and fish distribution.

3.2.1. Changes in hydro-climatic conditions

The southern part of the CCLME exhibits the most significant surface warming ever recorded from observations among all tropical Oceans (Figure 1), and the trend, computed for the 1982-2021 period, reaches 0.3 to 0.5 °C per decade.

Figure 1: Sea Surface Temperature trend in the tropical area showing that West Africa experiences the highest warming in this latitudinal range. The trend is computed for the 36 years from 1982 to 2017 using the Advanced Very-High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) Pathfinder v5.3 data set.

2.2.1.1. Environmental trends over 20-year biological sampling (1995-2015)

During the 20-year sea survey period, both trends in surface wind speed (SWS) and the upwelling index remained highly significant, particularly in the coastal domain of Mauritania (area 2) (Figure 2a, b). The upwelling index exhibited a positive and significant trend from North to South during the sea survey period (Figure 3b, solid line), consistent with the trend reported in the most extended time series (Figure 2b, dotted line).

The temperature data analysis reveals a lack of consistent and spatially homogeneous warming trends. A notable shift in SST occurred in 1994-95 (Figure 3d), marking a breakpoint in time. While no clear linear trend emerges across the whole period for all regions, localised and region-specific trends do exist (Figure 1d). However, these patterns lack large-scale temporal coherence, and the warming does not follow a simple, monotonic progression over time, making linear models inadequate for capturing such abrupt or regime-shift-like changes.

Figure 2. Spatial linear trends in hydro-climatic conditions in North West African coastal waters from 1995 to 2015 of a) the wind speed; b) the upwelling index trend; b') the latitudinal profile of the upwelling index as a reference; c) The chlorophyll-a concentration from SeaWiFS and MODIS-corrected data (computed from 1998; and d) the sea surface temperature (SST) from AVHRR. Black dots show significant trends (p -value < 0.05). The trend of the upwelling index for the entire 1988-2021 period is illustrated with a dotted line in panel b, superimposed to demonstrate temporal homogeneity in the upwelling increase compared to the 1995-2015 period.

2.2.1.2. Spatial variability of hydro-climatic conditions over 34 years in North West Africa

Since 1988, a highly significant intensification of upwelling intensity has been registered (Figure 2b) north of Cape Blanc (20°N), as well as in Mauritania (Sarré *et al.*, 2024). On the contrary, the Senegalese area showed a substantial drop up to 1999, followed by a second phase of moderate but regular increase. Accordingly, the SWS increase was highly significant in all areas from 1988 to 2021 (34 years; Figure 4a). The SSC showed no statistically significant changes in any area (Figure 3c) due to its high and contrasting variability on shorter temporal scales, except in Senegal, where a very significant

negative trend was observed. The increase was maximum between the peninsula of Cap-Vert (~14.7°N, Senegal) and Cape Blanc (~21.3°N, Mauritania) with a local pattern of ~0.4 °C decade⁻¹ during the past 40 years (Figure 3d, right panel). The SST increase was weaker in the northern part (0.1 to 0.3 °C decade⁻¹).

Figure 3. Changes in hydro-climatic conditions along the Northwest coast of Africa for five latitudinal areas (numbered 1 to 5 from North to South). Monthly averages (12-term moving averages) of a) the wind speed and b) upwelling index since 1988 (from CCMP satellite composite data); c) the chlorophyll-a concentration (SeaWiFS and MODIS-corrected data since 1998); and d) sea surface temperature since 1982 (AVHRR data) from Morocco (area 1) to Southern Senegal (area 5) until 2021 (four decades). Least-squares linear adjustments of trends are indicated by area and significance level (p-value: * > 0.05, ** > 0.01, *** > 0.001, and **** > 0.0001). All data were spatially averaged from the coast to 100 km offshore. The middle plots represent the average latitudinal profile of the time series. Maps (right panels) show the main values of the spatial trends per decade. The periods covered by the biological sampling survey (1995-2006, 2011, and 2015) are shaded in grey.

In the southern coastal CCLME, from 1982 to 2021, the impact of global warming was illustrated by the northward displacement of isotherms (Figure 4). The 24 °C isotherm shifted northwards off Senegal at a rate between 45 and 145 km per decade, according to the distance to the coast. The shift of the 22 °C isotherm is more important, especially near the coast, about 125 km in 20 years, with similar offshore displacements to the 24°C isotherm. Closer to the permanent upwelling region, the 20°

isotherm displacement is similar at the coast, while the offshore displacement is less important (75 km). This tendency persists for the 18.5 °C isotherm, particularly near the upwelling centres of the permanent upwelling region, *i.e.*, areas 3 and 4 in Figure 2, with displacements of 40 and 30 km, respectively.

Figure 4. Spatio-temporal shifts of sea surface isotherms in the southern Canary Current Upwelling System (1982-2021). (a) The black and red lines represent the average positions of isotherms 18.5, 20.0, 22.0, and 24.0 °C during the 1982-2001 (20 years) and 2002-2021 (20 years) periods, respectively. The background colours show the average sea surface temperature (SST) from 2002 to 2021. Coloured arrows illustrate the displacements of isotherms between both periods, distinguishing between coastal and offshore domains. The central "shift" frame provides the displacement distances in kilometres. (b) The corresponding SST anomaly (in °C) between the 20-year periods. Contoured black lines at 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 °C represent SST anomaly values, offering insight into the magnitude and spatial distribution of temperature variations over the analysed time frame.

All trends were tested for each of the four yearly time series of environmental variables and each latitudinal area (Figure 2). Most of them were highly significant, as detailed hereafter. The SST trends recorded during the biological sampling survey (BSS; acoustic observation and trawl sampling) period (1995-2015) did not show significant warming when aggregated by area. Nonetheless, high values of 0.3 °C decade⁻¹ were locally recorded off central southern Mauritania and Senegal (Figure 3d) despite stronger SWS in Mauritania. The SWS and upwelling index displayed a considerable increase across the entire region from 1988 to 2021, except for the upwelling index in Senegal (area 5), where overall stability was observed during this period. Over the longest time series, SSC trends along the sea survey period showed no significant trend, except in Senegal (area 5), where a significant decrease was observed (Figure 2c). This decrease was associated with the stability of the upwelling intensity (Figure 2b) and persistent sea warming (Figure 2d).

2.2.2. Changes in the distribution of sardinella

From the acoustic-based biomasses (from small pelagic assessment annual sea survey) of both sardinella, only *S. aurita* displayed a northward shift during the BSS period, while *S. maderensis* displayed a quasi-stable distribution over the same 20-year period. Moreover, a similar significant ($p < 0.01$) displacement of *S. aurita* northern limit computed from trawl catches is reported. This northern limit has moved northward at a significant rate of 181 km per decade since 1995 (Table 1).

Table 1. Northernmost detected latitude (°N) of the main pelagic species sampled during the annual stock assessment surveys, bootstrap of mean comparisons (time series equally divided, $n = 10\,000$) for the period 1995-2015. The significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) are marked in bold.

Species	Northern limits (°N)		Northward shift (km decade ⁻¹)	p-value
	1995-2001	2002-2015		
<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	27.2	29.1	181	***
<i>Sardinella maderensis</i>	24.0	25.2	114	-
<i>Chloroscombrus chrysurus</i>	18.5	20.4	195	***
<i>Caranx rhonchus</i>	23.8	24.5	70	*
<i>Brachydeuterus auritus</i>	18.9	19.6	78	*
<i>Selene dorsalis</i>	18.7	19.2	43	-
<i>Trachurus trecae</i>	24.4	26.3	197	*
<i>Sphyraena guachancho</i>	18.2	20.1	198	**

Figure 5. Hovmoller representation of the spatio-temporal changes in the spatial distribution of *Sardinella aurita* (a) and *S. maderensis* (b) during annual acoustics surveys in their distribution area. The northernmost detection of both species is plotted as a black line, based on data from 2,363 scientific trawl operations. The dotted sections of the lines represent periods without year-to-year surveys. Annual biomass is expressed in thousands of tons. The white area represents the 2011 survey without an acoustic biomass estimate. The blue line on the map shows the 200 m isobaths.

2.2.3. Changes in the distribution of other species

Other species than *S. aurita* also showed significant northward distribution shifts (Figure 6 and Table 1): *Trachurus trecae* moved regularly towards the north from 1995 to 2004 and then stopped its extension so that by the end of the observation period, its limit was found around 26°N. The northern limit of *C. chrysurus* was approximately 18.5°N in 1995 and had progressively shifted northward to 20.4°N in recent years, representing a distributional shift of 195 km per decade. No acoustic estimate was available for these species.

The distribution shift of *B. auritus* exhibited a slower but regular trend, resulting in a significant rate of 118 km per decade. *Brachydeuterus auritus* was not found north of 19°N in the surveys before 2000, but was reported five times after 2000. Similarly, the distribution area of *S. guachancho* gradually extended northward after 1995 (Figure 2), when its northern limit was located south of 18°N, and then expanded northward to 21°N in 2005-2006, representing a considerable shift of approximately 200 km per decade. The false scad (*C. rhonchus*) and *B. auritus* showed the slowest significant northward shift of the species considered in this study, with a speed of 70 km per decade. *Sardinella maderensis*, a tropical species, did not display any significant ($p > 0.05$) distributional shift (Figure 6), and *S. dorsalis* displayed a reasonably stable distribution area (Table 1). A shift distance close to 200 km per decade was observed for three species (*T. trecae*, *S. guachancho*, and *C. chrysurus*), showing similar northward extensions of their ranges of two hundred km per decade, a value precisely of the same order as that of *S. aurita*.

Figure 6. Changes in the distribution limits of the pelagic stocks of eight species sampled during the acoustic surveys from 1995 to 2015. Their northernmost limits were determined based on scientific trawl sampling data ($n = 2\ 263$). Solid lines represent significant trends ($p < 0.05$), while dotted lines indicate non-significant trends (see Table 1 for values).

2.2.4. Synthesis and discussion

Regardless of the period considered, the Cape Blanc region (~21.3°N, Mauritania) appears to be a transitional area regarding SST, separating a southern part characterised by a regular increase in SST (Figure 7). During the LEM period (long monitoring period 1985-2021), a significant SST trend (0.1 to 0.3 °C decade⁻¹) was observed throughout the year, both north and south of Cape Blanc (Figure 7). During the BSS period (1995-2015), these trends were similarly weak (compared to the LEM period) from April to August and again in November, with higher values in September and October, before dropping to negative values from December to March. These changes indicated that, despite some interdecadal variability and a likely shift in seasonality, the average warming remained weak (and comparable to the entire period) during the BSS period (Figure 2b).

We hypothesise that the exceptional SST warming observed from Mauritania to Senegal, the strongest ever recorded in the tropics during the LEM period, induced similar displacements for several species. The scientific catch data for *S. aurita* during the BSS period indicate a northward shift of 180 km over the studied period. The synergistic effects of climate variability and change on species fitness mediate small pelagic habitat suitability. It is well established that short-lived species, such as small pelagic fish, are highly sensitive to short-term environmental fluctuations, and these variations play a crucial role in shaping their distribution. However, the significance of considering the impact of long-term environmental changes on small pelagic fish habitats must be recognised. Over time, gradual environmental modifications can influence the overall habitat suitability of these species, whether combined with or independent of the effects of overfishing. Like *S. aurita*, five additional small pelagic fish species displayed significant northward trends in their distribution, while two others, including *S. maderensis*, exhibited no significant trend. As deduced from its acoustic-based biomass, *S. maderensis* displayed no significant shift in its northern limit and overall distribution.

DFN surveys indicate that *C. chrysurus*, *B. auritus*, and *S. guachancho* were moving beyond this boundary in the second part of the LEM period. The observed warming patterns appear to significantly influence the spatial restructuring of small pelagic fish populations, including *S. aurita*. Notably, the northern distances observed in the spatial shift of the pelagic fish (between 40 and ~200 km) align closely with the magnitude of the isotherm's displacements (40–145 km) since 1995 (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Comparative Sea Surface Temperature (SST) monthly trends (°C per decade) for the long environmental monitoring (LEM) period (1982-2021, solid lines) and the biological sampling survey (BSS) period (1995-2015 dotted lines), south and north of Cape Blanc (red and blue lines, respectively), showing that the SST anomaly during the sampling period (centered in November) was similar to the average yearly anomaly, for both periods.

The trend in *S. aurita* biomass showed that the portion of the stock north of Cape Blanc increased from 38 to 65% between 1995 and 2015 (Figure 7), with a significant difference ($p < 0.001$) between the first and last parts of the time series. Notably, the northern part (Figure 2b, area 1), characterised by a strong summer coastal upwelling (Benazzouz *et al.*, 2014), was the region with one of the greatest increases in SWS intensity across the entire Canary Current ecosystem over the last 34 years, including the BSS period. To examine the hypothesis of a northern population displacement (Figure 8) triggered by strong and/or rapid environmental changes, particularly the quick rise in SST observed in 1994-95 and the intensified upwelling in 1998 (Figure 2b, d), we employed two distinct bootstrap procedures. Across all analyses, we consistently observed significant to highly significant changes in SWS and upwelling index in all areas. In contrast, no change was recorded for SCC, except in the Senegal area. SST exhibited a significant change only during the LEM period, not in the BSS one.

Figure 8. Relative variation of *Sardinella aurita* biomass and the main hydro-climatic conditions from 1995 to 2015, North and South of Cape Blanc - a pivotal zone separating the region of permanent upwelling from the subtropical region of seasonal upwelling. The percentage of *S. aurita* biomass north of Cape Blanc (black solid line) has increased in the recent part of the time series. The linear trends of the coastal upwelling index (blue lines), chlorophyll-a (green lines), and sea surface temperature (SST, red lines) exhibit an overall increase in upwelling conditions in both sectors. Additionally, a noticeable decrease in chlorophyll-a was observed south of Cape Blanc, whereas no significant trends in SST were identified.

While the entire CCLME was notably impacted by long-term warming, the heightened upwelling in the northern part of the region (North of Cape Blanc) mitigates coastal heating and maintains productivity. Consequently, this area offers more favourable habitat conditions and a relatively stable thermal environment for small pelagics. In stark contrast, the southern part of the system (Senegal) experiences a modest increase in SST coupled with a decline in phytoplanktonic biomass. It implies that this region is likely becoming a less productive habitat for some species. The acoustic biomasses of *S. aurita* and *S. maderensis* during the BSS period (Figure 9) indicated that the biomass of *S. aurita*

was decreasing, with the lowest value observed in the last year (2015). This decline has continued in recent years (FAO, 2023). During these 21 years, the average SWS north of Cape Blanc was higher than 7 m s^{-1} , well over the optimum environmental window of 5 m s^{-1} defined for the recruitment success of small pelagic fishes (Diankha *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, environmental conditions are likely not favourable for all species, as indicated by their reproductive success (Baldé *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 9. Acoustic biomasses of *Sardinella aurita* and *S. maderensis* (expressed in nautical area scattering coefficient 'NASC', $\text{m}^2 \text{ nmi}^{-2}$) obtained from the sea survey annual assessment exercise from 1995-2015, adding 2011 and 2015 carried out by the FRV Dr Fridtjof Nansen in North West African waters (Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and The Gambia).

Brachydeuterus auritus, *C. chrysurus*, *S. dorsalis*, and *S. guachancho* are known to be present in brackish waters during their juvenile stage (Sloterdijk *et al.*, 2017). For this reason, their northern border of distribution remains mainly south of the Cape Verde Frontal Zone and notably further south than those of the other species considered in this study (Figure 3), which thrive in the richest part of the coastal upwelling, beyond the transition zone between the southern and northern CCLME. In particular, *S. dorsalis* did not exhibit significant movement. This species is considered semi-demersal, or "the least pelagic" among the eight selected in this study.

These observed spatial shifts in *S. aurita*, particularly its northward expansion and varying biomass along the coast, highlight the importance of developing and applying models that can simulate future changes in species' distribution limits, relative biomass, and range dynamics. **This motivates the exploration of high-resolution scenario-based projections, as presented in Section 4.3, to assess how *S. aurita* might respond to continued climate forcing across the region.**

2.3. Climate extreme impacts on the marine ecosystem in North West Africa

In the Northwest African coastal region, strong interannual SST variability has been discovered, known as Dakar Niño (Oettli *et al.*, 2016), which occurs around the Senegal-Mauritania Frontal Zone (*e.g.*, Koseki *et al.*, 2024). As this climate extreme event was relatively recently discovered, there are still open questions, for example, how such climate extreme events affect regional marine ecosystem activity. To answer this question, we first analysed GLORYS reanalysis data and the Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative (OC-CCI) satellite product. We assessed the performance of the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) coupled with the Finite Volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2) simulation of the pre-final cycle productions (hereafter referred to as IFS-FESOM; Rackow *et al.*, 2024). Report to section 2 and or the DKRZ website (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/prefinal.html>) for details on simulation names. Note that these are free-running model simulations; therefore, their temporal evolution cannot be directly compared to the observations.

As shown in Figure 10, we identified the Dakar Niño and Niña events from the Dakar Index (Oettli *et al.*, 2016; Koseki *et al.*, 2024) for the GLORYS reanalysis and IFS-FESOM simulation. The index is defined as SST anomalies averaged over the region $21^{\circ}\text{--}17^{\circ}\text{W}$, $9^{\circ}\text{--}14^{\circ}\text{N}$, and events are determined when the February-March-April averaged index exceeds ± 0.8 standard deviations. During the Dakar Niños, the SST increases, reaching its largest value of 2 degrees, located around 12°N and 18°W (Figure 11a). Its spatial scale is limited to the coastal region of Northwest Africa. While Oettli *et al.* (2016) concluded

that surface heat flux is one of the main drivers for the warm events, Koseki *et al.* (2024) suggested that vertical motion in the upper ocean tends to be reduced during the warm events.

Figure 10. Detrended Dakar Index (SST averaged over 9N-14N and 20W-17W) for (a) GLOREY reanalysis from 1998 to 2023 and (b) IFS-FESOM simulation from 1990 to 2020. Dakar Niño (warm) / Niña (cold) events are defined as the Index being more / less than \pm standard deviation, as noted by the orange and blue dots in the plot.

Figure 11. Composite anomalies of Dakar Niño for (a) GLOREY SST, (b) surface chlorophyll-a from OC-CI, and (c) IFS-FESOM SST. The events of Dakar Niño are illustrated in Figure 10.

As shown in Figure 11b, the Dakar Niños generate surface chlorophyll-*a* anomalies. Interestingly, along the coast, phytoplankton tends to increase, even though coastal upwelling is expected to be suppressed during the warm events, as suggested by Koseki *et al.* (2024). Additionally, a positive production anomaly is detected around 20°N. This activation at higher latitudes could be consistent with the results of López-Parages *et al.* (2020), who showed that sardinella, a pelagic fish in this region, moves northward following SST warming associated with the Pacific El Niño. In contrast, ecosystem activity is suppressed offshore, indicating that low-trophic-level marine ecosystem activity is more confined along the coast during warm events. In the case of cold events (Dakar Niñas, not shown), the anomaly pattern is reversed: the activity is suppressed along the coast and enhanced offshore, indicating that the active ecosystem is spread widely. This result suggests that higher trophic level ecosystems respond to the anomalous spatial pattern of phytoplankton, providing valuable information for local fisheries.

The IFS-FESOM simulation is capable of realistically reproducing Dakar Niño events, although its amplitude is overestimated (Figure 11c). Compared to the GLOREY reanalysis, the warm SST anomaly

has a limited spatial extent; however, the latitudinal location of the warm SST is correctly reproduced, which is attributed to the better-resolved Senegal-Mauritania Frontal Zone in IFS-FESOM. This is an advantage of the nextGEMS model over CMIP6 and High-ResMIP models, which have difficulty resolving the coastal upwelling (*e.g.*, Sylla *et al.*, 2020). We will assess the performance of the IFS-FESOM simulation for marine ecosystems in Section 4.2 by implementing a deep learning methodology (Section 3).

4. Reconstruction of SSC using AI from nextGEMS IFS-FESOM simulation

4.1. The deep learning approach to reconstructing future SSC time series

A vital prerequisite for accurately identifying the impacts of climate change on marine ecosystems is the ability to confidently detect anthropogenic signals in phytoplankton biomass. However, the temporally short satellite and spatially scarce *in situ* records have so far prevented us from elucidating the spatio-temporal variations of phytoplankton biomass beyond the interannual timescales. On the modelling front, large uncertainties remain related to the complex and delicate balance between bottom-up (*i.e.*, physical) processes and top-down (zooplankton grazing) control, which drives the fate of phytoplankton at these timescales. These processes are not fully understood and are variously parameterised across biogeochemical models. Furthermore, while the nextGEMS models do not include biogeochemical models, this deliverable also incorporates results from ICON-O coupled with the HAMOCC biogeochemical model (see Section 5), thereby expanding the range of explored processes beyond the physical drivers used in our deep-learning approach.

Observations and models, however, have demonstrated that bottom-up processes strongly influence the spatiotemporal distribution of phytoplankton biomass over a significant portion of the global ocean. Thus, our approach to overcome the above issues is as follows:

- i) implement deep learning (DL) schemes to learn relationships between physical predictors (from the high resolution-1/12° GLORYS reanalysis) vs. SSC from radiometric satellite observations (hereafter referred to as SSC_{Sat}) over one decade (step 1 in Figure 12)
- ii) apply our best-performing DL scheme to GLORYS physical outputs to reconstruct the SSC time-series over the radiometric era and compare with the SSC observations to validate the reconstruction (step 2 in Figure 12)
- iii) Apply the DL scheme to physical outputs from the IFS-FESOM historical and future projections (step 3 in Figure 12) to investigate the SSC low-frequency variability and anthropogenic trends from an SR-ESM, and then compare with SSC predictions from low and medium-resolution CMIP6 ESMs.

Figure 12. Schematic of the deep-learning methodology to reconstruct SSC time series.

The skills of two deep-learning methods to reconstruct SSC_{sat} are investigated. First, we utilise a baseline Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture, as described in Roussillon *et al.* (2023). The considered CNN architecture comprises 2D convolutional layers, each employing a 3x3 kernel size, a stride of 1x1, and 1x1 padding. After each convolutional layer, a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function is applied. Second, a UNet architecture, initially developed for biomedical image segmentation (Ronneberger *et al.*, 2015), has proven highly effective for pixel-wise regression tasks in oceanography, such as predicting SSC from physical variable maps (Martinez-Balbontin *et al.*, 2025 preprint, Lakra *et al.*, submitted). UNet employs a symmetric encoder-decoder structure with skip connections. This approach should enable precise localization of submesoscale features while maintaining basin-wide patterns (context awareness). The input consists of multichannel physical variable maps (SST, SSS, SSH, MLD, and surface currents), and the output is a single-channel SSC map. The architecture's ability to preserve spatial coherence through skip connections is expected to be superior to traditional CNNs for resolving sharp SSC gradients associated with oceanic fronts.

Steps 1 and 2, as described above, were carried out using two methods: CNN and UNet. Their ability to reconstruct SSC_{sat} was compared, and the UNet proved to be more effective. Therefore, the results presented below were obtained using the UNet. Two simulations are carried out with step 1 in common. Then, SSC is reconstructed from physical predictors, either from the GLORYS reanalysis or from the IFS-FESOM model (steps 2 and 3).

4.2. Sub-regional application: North-West Africa

The direct comparison of SSC_{sat} with the reconstructed SSC can only be made using the simulation with GLORYS predictors for reconstruction (step 2), as GLORYS is a forced reanalysis. This means that GLORYS outputs on day J are expected to be temporally (and spatially) aligned with the observations of day J. In contrast, this is not the case for the IFS-FESOM outputs, which are from a coupled ocean-atmosphere model. The temporal correlation map over the reconstruction period (2010–2024) between the DL-reconstructed SSC and SSC_{sat} shows an excellent correlation and reconstruction of SSC in the northern part of the area, with a more moderate correlation between 15°N and 20°N, and south of 2°N (Figure 13, right panel). The moderate and low correlations in SSC reconstruction are illustrated by the two time series in Figure 13 (left panels, red crosses in the right panel). At 25°N, both seasonal and interannual variations in SSC are reconstructed, although the extrema are underestimated. At 10°N, where the correlation is low, SSC_{sat} exhibits high-frequency variability that is barely reconstructed.

As phytoplankton biomass exhibits contrasting temporal variability, it is essential to characterise the sub-seasonal, seasonal, and multi-annual signals observed in SSC_{sat} to assess which temporal scales are reconstructed by our DL approaches. Here, we apply a temporal decomposition procedure (similar to that in Keerthi *et al.*, 2020) to satellite ocean colour observations from the Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative (OC-CCI) (Sathyendranath *et al.*, 2019) to analyse the temporal variability of SSC_{sat} . We then compare the temporal components derived from the DL-reconstructed SSC with those obtained from the satellite observations.

Figure 14 (left column) illustrates the SSC_{sat} variability derived from the 0.25° spatial resolution and weekly temporal resolution dataset. The seasonal component captures periodic variability on timescales ranging from approximately three months to one year. Data gaps caused by cloud cover in the satellite product were filled using linear interpolation before performing the decomposition. The multiannual component represents low-frequency variability associated with timescales exceeding eight months. The sub-seasonal component encompasses higher-frequency variability within the 8–88 day band, along with irregular fluctuations at frequencies beyond this range.

Overall, the seasonal and subseasonal components together account for approximately 80% of the total variance, while the multiannual component contributes around 20% across the basin. Seasonal variability is most pronounced in the northern latitudes, where it explains over 60% of the total variance. In the upwelling region, seasonal and subseasonal components contribute roughly equally.

In contrast, subseasonal variability dominates in the southern latitudes, explaining more than 60% of the total variance. Although multiannual variability remains relatively weak across the domain, it exhibits slightly elevated contributions in the southern regions.

Figure 13. Correlation map of the UNet reconstructed Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a (SSC) using GLORYS as predictors, against the observed satellite-derived SSC (SSC_{Sat}) from the Ocean Colour Climate Change Initiative (OC-CI, hereafter referred to as "OC") for the test period 2010-2024 (right panel). Two selected time series are displayed on the left, located at the red crosses on the correlation maps (locations in the panel's title).

Figure 14. Time-scale decomposition of sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC) variance over 2012-2024 from (left column) satellite-derived SSC (SSC_{Sat}) observations, and reconstructed SSC from (middle column) GLORYS predictors and (right column) IFS-FESOM predictors. Percentage of the SSC variance explained by its (top) year-to-year varying seasonal, (middle) subseasonal and (bottom) multi-annual components.

The two UNet simulations (both trained on GLORYS predictors), which reconstruct SSC from GLORYS (Figure 14, middle column) or IFS-FESOM (Figure 14, right column) predictors, reproduce similar spatial patterns to SSC_{Sat} . In both reconstructions, seasonal and sub-seasonal components account for the majority of the total variance, while the multiannual signal remains relatively limited ($\sim 20\%$). However, seasonal variability is somewhat overestimated in the DL reconstructions, particularly along the upwelling zones, where it explains more than 60% of the variance, unlike in the satellite observations. While in both DL-reconstructed SSC, the subseasonal variability dominates in the southern latitudes according to SSC_{Sat} , their overestimation of the seasonal signal off the coasts of Mauritania and Senegal occurs at the expense of the subseasonal one. Finally, the slightly better reproduction of the SSC_{Sat} interannual variability when based on IFS-FESOM predictors rather than GLORYS ones augurs well for SSC climate projections based on IFS-FESOM.

4.3. Global application

As illustrated in the previous section, the variance in the SSC signal occurs on several scales (sub-seasonal to multi-annual). In this section, we assess the extent to which these signals are present at a global scale, depending on the spatio-temporal resolution of the distributed SSC_{Sat} satellite products. When SSC_{Sat} data are based on a 0.25° weekly resolution, seasonal and subseasonal variability together account for more than 70% of the total variance, with pronounced regional differences (Figure 15). Seasonal variability is most dominant in the subtropical regions. In subpolar areas, the seasonal and subseasonal components contribute more equally, whereas in tropical regions, the subseasonal component accounts for a relatively larger share. The multi-annual component generally plays a minor role across most regions, except in the tropical Pacific, where ENSO dominates and has a strong impact on the positions of the South Pacific Convergence Zone and the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone.

Figure 15. Variance from satellite-derived sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC_{Sat}) observations with four spatio-temporal resolutions. Percentage of the SSC_{Sat} variance explained by its (top) year-to-year varying seasonal, (middle) subseasonal and (bottom) multi-annual components.

When the spatial resolution is coarsened from 0.25° to 1° (second column), the contribution of subseasonal variability decreases slightly (by less than 10%), with a corresponding marginal increase in both the seasonal and multi-annual components. As expected, coarsening the temporal resolution from weekly to monthly (third column) results in a much more pronounced decline in subseasonal variability (by over 20%) alongside increased contributions from the seasonal and multi-annual components. This suggests that temporal resolution has a much stronger influence than spatial resolution on the representation of these variability scales. Furthermore, the variance distributions for the 0.25° monthly and 1° monthly products are nearly identical, indicating that temporal resolution is

more important than spatial resolution in capturing mesoscale dynamics. These results emphasise the importance of utilising observations with the highest time resolution in regions where subseasonal processes are dominant, while coarser products may be sufficient at the global scale for investigating the low-frequency variability of SSC.

5. Projected changes in marine ecosystems: nextGEMS

To investigate the impacts of climate change on the marine ecosystem, we utilise the IFS-FESOM simulation, which extends to 2050 under the SSP 3.70 scenario (step 3, Figure 12), to make comparisons with CMIP6 low-resolution models. Results from the Senegalese region have highlighted the challenges of the AI approach in reconstructing submesoscale dynamics. This may be because ocean observations used to learn about the links with SSC do not exist at these high spatio-temporal scales (25 km, for instance, for sea level anomalies vs. 4 km for SSC). This is why we used the GLORYS oceanic reanalysis to train the neural network, although outputs are not entirely aligned in space and time with SSC_{sat} at the submesoscale. Consequently, that part of the signal (*i.e.*, the sub-mesoscale) is poorly learned and poorly reconstructed, which strongly impacts the results in some regions.

We have reconstructed the SSC for the IFS-FESOM projections in three steps (see Figure 12):

Step 1: The UNet is trained over 2003-2009 on GLORYS physical outputs and OC-CCI satellite SSC: 1) on a 1° monthly grid at global scale, and 2) on a 9 km weekly grid for the Senegalese region.

Step 2: SSC is reconstructed from GLORYS physical outputs on a 1° monthly grid on the global scale and on a 9 km weekly grid for the Senegalese region from 2003 to 2023, to compare the reconstructed SSC with the OC-CCI satellite SSC and assess the reconstruction skills (see Section 3).

Step 3: SSC is reconstructed from IFS-FESOM outputs on a 1° monthly grid at a global scale and on a 9 km weekly grid for the Senegalese region from 1990 to 2050.

Our approach considers that 1) it is extremely time and energy consuming to reconstruct SSC at a global scale at a 9 km resolution, 2) that we are more interested in longer timescales of variability than the submesoscale, and 3) recognizes that the interannual signal is more apparent in the SSC_{sat} 1° monthly product (Figure 15).

5.1. Global marine productivity

One potential limitation of the comparison between the IFS-FESOM-based SSC reconstruction and the SSC derived from CMIP6 models lies in the difference in scenarios used in the respective modelling exercises. Most CMIP6 climate models that include a biogeochemical component have been run under the SSP5-8.5 or SSP1-2.6 scenarios (both ends of the scenarios' spectrum), whereas the IFS-FESOM projection follows the SSP3-7.0 scenario. Nevertheless, the comparison between projections under SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 remains scientifically justifiable for the time horizon extending to mid-century (year 2050). Although these Shared Socioeconomic Pathways differ in their long-term assumptions regarding socioeconomic development and emissions trajectories, they exhibit relatively similar radiative forcing levels and greenhouse gas concentrations up to 2050. This is clearly illustrated in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (Figure 16), which shows that global indicators—such as mean temperature, sea level anomaly, and precipitation—remain broadly comparable across the two scenarios until the latter half of the century, after which a more pronounced divergence occurs. Therefore, for near- to mid-term analyses, particularly those focusing on climate impacts and adaptation strategies, comparisons across these scenarios could be considered robust and informative.

Global mean SSC comparisons between CMIP6 projections (derived from models with interactive ocean biogeochemistry modules) and the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection (with SSC produced via deep learning applied to physical outputs) are presented in Figures 17 and 18. Figure 17 highlights the temporal evolution of SSC, while Figure 18 illustrates the spatial patterns of simulated climate trends around mid-century. As previously reported, biogeochemical projections from CMIP6 climate models (which include interactive ocean biogeochemistry components) are subject to considerable

uncertainty, with inter-model differences often exceeding those between emission scenarios, and show only limited improvement relative to the earlier CMIP5 ensemble (Bopp *et al.*, 2013; Kwiatkowski *et al.*, 2020). This uncertainty is evident in Figure 17, which displays SSC trends from 1990 to 2050 across CMIP6 models. While most models simulate a weak and statistically insignificant negative trend, some show either a slight increase in SSC or substantial positive or negative trends (notably in simulations based on the CanESM and MPI models, respectively), resulting in low confidence in the robustness of the projected changes. Among these CMIP-based projections, the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection exhibits (i) a negligible long-term trend and (ii) weak interannual variability, as already noted in the previous section.

Figure 16: Mean global temperature anomaly (a), precipitation (b) and sea level anomaly (d) from the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report.

Figure 17. Seasonal anomaly of sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC) relative to the period 1990-2050 for the global Ocean between 50°S and 50°N. The lines are the median for the box computed for 15 Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) SSP5-8.5 models and for the reconstructed SSC using the UNet and IFS-FESOM physical predictors on a 1° monthly grid.

Given the widespread global SSC trend projections for 2050 (Figure 17), comparing the spatial patterns between CMIP projections and our IFS-FESOM-based projection may help identify spatial trends common to these different approaches, thereby increasing the relative robustness of those specific trends. However, Figure 18 shows that among the 14 CMIP projections compared to our IFS-FESOM-based projected SSC, none are truly comparable in terms of spatial structure and amplitude. Indeed, the IFS-FESOM-based projected SSC trends for 2050 are quite weak compared to most CMIP projections, except for those from the CMCC model. However, a closer look at the CMCC spatial structures reveals disagreement in high-latitude regions. The closest match in terms of spatial pattern is found with the CNRM-ESM2-1 model, although it shows a stronger amplitude.

Therefore, among the wide range of CMIP model projections, the IFS-FESOM-based projected SSC does not converge with any single forecast at the global scale, and thus does not aid in identifying robust future outcomes.

Figure 18. Spatial distribution of sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC) seasonal anomalies for the 2030-2050 period relative to 1990-2020, on a monthly 1° grid. The upper left panel displays the UNet reconstruction of SSC using IFS-FESOM physical parameters with the SSP3-7.0 scenario. The remaining 14 panels show Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) climate models with the SSP5-8.5 scenario.

5.2. Sub-regional marine productivity

4.2.1 Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a concentration (SSC)

Quantitative projections from ESMs are subject to considerable uncertainty, particularly at regional and local scales (Friedrich *et al.*, 2012; Frölicher *et al.*, 2014; Hauck *et al.*, 2015; Roy *et al.*, 2011; Tjiputra *et al.*, 2014; Terhaar *et al.*, 2021), where less averaging is done and different individual mechanisms dominate other regions. The spatially averaged SSC projections in the West African region from CMIP6 models and the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection display a high spread (primarily due to the highly negative trends of the MPI models), yet with no model predicting an increase in SSC in mid-century and most models predicting negligible trends (Figure 19). In comparison to those projections, the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection also displays near-zero trends, therefore agreeing with most CMIP6 models. Nevertheless, interannual variability of the IFS-FESOM-based forecast is lower than in most CMIP6 models.

Despite the relative agreement of the spatially integrated trends from most CMIP6 models and the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection, the spatial patterns of those respective projections are not consistent (Figure 20). Indeed, despite a relatively common north-south dipole, most CMIP6 models display highly different spatial patterns, with sometimes antagonistic patterns, as seen in the CanESM and MPI-based projections. Moreover, the IFS-FESOM-based projection displays an increase in the SSC following the coastline, which does not agree with any of the CMIP6 model projections and may be related to its higher spatial resolution. It is interesting to note that similar SSC coastal anomalies are also commonly found when computing trends from satellite data (Demarcq, 2009). A new sensor-corrected SSC data series, computed from satellite data for the 26 years from 1998 to 2023 within nextGEMS (not shown), displays consistent coastal positive SSC trends in Morocco and Guinea, as well as coastal negative trends in Mauritania and Senegal, with patterns similar to those of the FESOM-based projection.

Figure 19. Seasonal anomaly of sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC) relative to the period 1990-2020 for the West African box [30W, 5W] and [0N,35N]. The lines are the median for the box computed for 15 Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) SSP8.5 models and for the reconstructed SSC using the UNet and IFS-FESOM physical predictors.

Figure 20. Spatial distribution of sea surface chlorophyll-a (SSC) seasonal anomalies for the 2030-2050 period relative to 1990-2020, for the West African box [30W, 5W] and [0N,35N]. The upper left panel displays the UNet reconstruction of SSC using IFS-FESOM physical parameters with the ssp3.7 scenario. The other 14 panels show Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) climate models with the ssp8.5 scenario.

Despite the relative agreement of the spatially integrated trends from most CMIP6 models and the IFS-FESOM-based SSC projection, the spatial patterns of those respective projections are not consistent (Figure 20). Indeed, despite a relatively common north-south dipole, most CMIP6 models display highly

different spatial patterns, with sometimes antagonistic patterns, as seen in the CanESM and MPI-based projections. Moreover, the IFS-FESOM-based projection shows an increase in the SSC following the coastline, which does not agree with any of the CMIP model projections and may be related to its higher spatial resolution. It is interesting to note that similar SSC coastal anomalies are also commonly found when computing trends from satellite data (Demarcq, 2009). A new sensor-corrected SSC data series, computed from satellite data for the 26 years from 1998 to 2023 within nextGEMS (not shown), displays consistent coastal positive SSC trends in Morocco and Guinea, as well as coastal negative trends in Mauritania and Senegal, with patterns similar to those of the FESOM-based projection.

On a global scale, the discrepancies between the CMIP model and the IFS-FESOM-based projections do not allow for the identification of robust future outcomes in the north-west African region. Learning from the predictors and SSC values in the CMIP6 model may allow us to quantify uncertainties due to differences in ocean physics versus those due to the biogeochemical component.

4.2.2. Small pelagic fish schools

Small pelagic fish are sensitive to environmental changes (Poloczanska *et al.*, 2016). Previous studies conducted off the southern part of the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem (sCCLME) have highlighted changes in the abundance and distribution limits of several fish species in response to oceanographic variability, including changes linked to cooling or warming waters (Hofstede *et al.*, 2007; Sarré *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, modelling the effects of oceanographic factors on fish school density is crucial for understanding the dynamics of marine ecosystems. This study investigates how acoustic fish school density varied in response to key environmental drivers over the period 1995-2015. The bias from fish avoidance behaviour in front of the research vessel (Brehmer *et al.*, 2019) was assumed to be constant over time and thus not to affect the observed temporal trends in school density. In this regard, we used acoustic sea surveys conducted in the sCCLME, complemented by environmental satellite data.

The acoustic surveys were the same as those used in sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3, here covering the region from southern Senegal (12°N) to Mauritania (28°N). Acoustic data were processed and analysed using Matecho software (Perrot *et al.*, 2018). Fish school extraction was conducted using an algorithm integrated within Matecho, applying a S_v threshold of -55 dB. Environmental data include annual averages of SST, Ekman transport index (Eke) from IFS-FESOM simulations, and SSC derived from IFS-FESOM-based reconstruction. To estimate the influence of environmental variables on variations in fish stock density, generalised additive models (GAMs) were fitted using the “mgcv” package in R. A Gaussian distribution with an identity link function was specified. Smooth terms were modelled using thin-plate regression splines ($bs = 'tp'$), with a basis dimension (k) set to 3 for each term to allow adequate flexibility while avoiding overfitting. We used the nautical area scattering coefficient (NASC) as a proxy of relative fish density. NASC is widely used in fisheries acoustics to quantify the integrated acoustic backscatter of pelagic organisms and is expressed in square meters per nautical mile squared ($m^2 \text{ nmi}^2$). The response variable in the model was the logarithmically transformed NASC. For the model selection procedure, different models were fitted using the REML method, and their performance was evaluated using key statistical measures, including adjusted R^2 , explained deviance, and Akaike information criterion (AIC). The final model was chosen based on its lowest AIC and highest explanatory power. For model validation, residual diagnostics were also performed to validate the model assumptions. Finally, based on the model that best fits our response variable (log-transformed NASC), we used projected environmental variables to generate future scenarios for changes in fish relative densities from 1995 to 2050. The final model was specified as follows:

$$\text{Log (NASC)} = \alpha + s(\text{SST}, k = 3) + s(\text{Year}, k = 3) + \text{ti}(\text{Eke}, \text{SSC}, k = c(3, 3))$$

The final model showed a strong fit to the data, with predicted values closely aligning with observations (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Observed versus predicted fish school density (NASC values) from the final Generalised Additive Model (GAM).

The final GAM model explained 91.2% of the variance, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.821, indicating strong explanatory power. The interaction between Eke and SSC (modelled using a smoothed tensor product) was statistically significant (p -value = 0.008). Interannual variability, modelled as a smoothed term for the year, was highly significant (p -value = 0.003). In contrast, SST showed a marginal effect (p -value = 0.095).

The significant interaction between Ekman transport and SSC is the most influential predictor, reflecting a synergy between the intensity of upwelling and primary productivity. Primary production is actively driven by upwelling, thus modulating the availability of food for pelagic fish (Demarcq, 2009). SST showed a marginal but ecologically relevant non-linear effect. Colder SSTs generally indicate more intense upwelling (Capet *et al.*, 2016; Faye *et al.*, 2015; Ndoye *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, the marginal effect of SST in the model might be due to its collinearity with Ekman transport. Nevertheless, this reinforces the interpretation that the dynamics of upwelling determine productivity. Annual temporal variability was also significant, suggesting long-term trends or interannual climate variability (*e.g.*, NAO, ENSO) influencing fish abundance beyond the environmental variables in the model (Thiaw *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 22: Predicted annual variation in relative fish school density based on a Generalised Additive Model (GAM) using Ekman transport (Eke), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), and Sea Surface chlorophyll-*a* (SSC) as environmental predictors from IFS-FESOM-derived datasets. Blue curve represents the observed acoustic-based total NASC (nautical area scattering coefficient). Red curve shows the predicted fish NASC density. The dashed red line represents the trend of predicted NASC, while the shaded red ribbon illustrates the 95% confidence interval of the predictions.

Using the GAM model, general trends in fish stock density were predicted for the period 1995–2015, serving as a basis for projections up to 2050 (Figure 22). The results show a marked and persistent decline in fish school density, characterised by a continuous and progressive decrease, representing a reduction of approximately $3.10^7 \text{ m}^2 \text{ nmi}^{-2}$ by 2050. These temporal dynamics are consistent with the impacts of climate change on the distribution and abundance of small pelagic fish in the region. They are attributed to the intensification of upwelling and SST warming (Sarre *et al.*, 2024). However, it is essential to consider the model's limitations and the uncertainties associated with the projections. While this model focuses on environmental predictors, it does not account for anthropogenic

pressures, which are major contributors to the declines in small pelagic fish biomass (Belhabib *et al.*, 2015; Diankha *et al.*, 2018).

Additionally, the projections involve uncertainties inherent in climate models and the complex dynamics of ecosystems. In summary, our results highlight a significant decline trend for small pelagic fish schools, mainly driven by environmental dynamics and interannual variability. Such results reinforce the need for an ecosystem-based management of fisheries to ensure the sustainability of these key economic resources in North West Africa.

4.2.3. SSL micronekton spatial distribution and biomass

As introduced in Section 2.1, Sound Scattering Layers (SSLs) are the result of acoustic scattering from extensive aggregations of micronekton and large zooplankton (to simplify hereafter only micronektonic) (Behagle *et al.*, 2017). In an oceanic environment, micronektonic play an essential role (Brodeur *et al.*, 2019), providing the main link between primary producers and higher trophic levels in the marine food web. Micronekton are sensitive to environmental changes (Gibson *et al.*, 2009; Hays *et al.*, 2005). Due to the short life cycles of these species, intermediate communities respond rapidly to mesoscale physical processes associated with currents and frontal structures linked to coastal upwelling (Ndoye *et al.*, 2017). Micronektonic organisms are essential for sustaining organisms higher up the food web (Behagle *et al.*, 2017; Benoit-Bird and Au, 2004; Sato and Benoit-Bird, 2017); consequently, changes to their community could impact the whole marine ecosystem (Algueró-Muñiz *et al.*, 2017).

4.2.3.1. SSL Spatial distribution

Here we examine the spatial distribution of micronekton in the southern part of the sCCLME and analyse the long-term variability of micronekton relative to pelagic density using acoustic data. The acoustic surveys were conducted in the same manner as described in Sarré *et al.* (2024) (see Section 2.2.2), covering the region from southern Senegal (12°16') to Morocco (32°30' N). Acoustic data were echo-integrated per 0.1 nautical miles (nmi) using 'Matecho' (Perrot *et al.*, 2018). To obtain homogeneous data, only continental shelf data were considered (*i.e.*, 10–150 m). The relative acoustic density, expressed as the Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient (NASC or s_A , $m^2 \text{ nmi}^2$) (MacLennan *et al.*, 2002), was used as a proxy for marine organism biomass to assess spatial variability. SSL micronekton were extracted using a threshold of -80 dB, meaning that SSLs with acoustic volume backscattering strengths (S_v in dB) below this threshold were excluded from the analysis. The distribution of total acoustic density divides the study area into two parts: north and south, separated by Cap Blanc (20.75°N). To detect spatial changes in the spatial distribution of pelagic marine organisms in the areas north and south of Cap Blanc, we analysed the barycenter displacements of micronekton over the time series. The analysis of the micronekton's relative acoustic density barycenter displacement revealed no significant overall trends (Figure 23). However, inter-annual fluctuations were observed south of Cap Blanc, where barycenter positions exhibited high variability.

Figure 23: Spatio-temporal distribution of micronekton relative acoustic density (NASC) from 1995 to 2015 in North West Africa (Morocco to Senegal) (Survey R/V Fridtjof Nansen).

Acoustic density in the southern region generally exceeded that of the northern region between approximately 1995 and 2005 (Figure 24). Furthermore, between 2010 and 2015, the southern region experienced a significant increase in acoustic density, reaching the highest values recorded in the database, while the northern region remained relatively lower throughout this period. No significant trend was observed in the Micronekton relative density during the study period (p -value > 0.05) in the sCCLME. As a perspective for future work, we aim to assess the influence of key environmental drivers on the vertical and spatial structure of micronekton.

Figure 14: Total relative micronekton pelagic biomass (expressed as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient NASC, $m^2 nmi^{-2}$) in North and South Cap Blanc, from 1995 to 2015 in North West Africa (Morocco to Senegal) (Survey R/V Fridtjof Nansen).

Diel changes were observed in the sCCLME, reflecting a regular diel vertical migration DVM pattern: micronekton density increased during the night. The day-night difference in micronekton relative density was significant (p -value < 0.000). Δ_{DVM} (i.e., night–day) mainly produced values, with higher NASC densities at night compared to day (Figure 26). Δ_{DVM} was higher in the south compared to the north of Cap Blanc. The DVM trend was also evaluated over the 20 years using Δ_{DVM} . No significant trends were reported in either area for all groups.

Figure 25: Effect of diel vertical migration (DVM) on the micronekton relative pelagic biomass within the water column in the areas north (top) and south of Cap Blanc (down) in the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem. The shaded area represents the standard deviations.

Figure 26: Differences between day and night micronekton diel vertical migration relative acoustic density " Δ_{DVM} ", expressed in Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient noted NASC or S_A , $m^2 nmi^{-2}$, reflecting the diel vertical migration (DVM).

The more pronounced DVM (higher positive Δ_{DVM}) in the south of Cap Blanc suggests that this area is primarily populated by communities that perform DVM, particularly those involving fish. However, the absence of a clear DVM trend allows us to confirm that key functional pelagic groups remain stable in the system over the study period. Despite environmental variability, particularly in terms of SST and upwelling, no long-term changes were detected in micronekton density or behaviour, highlighting the ecological stability of the mid-trophic level in the sCCLME.

Given the observed patterns in our study area (sCCLME), we consider it a relevant case for testing climate change projections of micronekton relative density. Although no significant shift was detected in the barycenter of micronekton during the study period (p -value > 0.05), the acoustic biomass in the southern region showed a marked increasing trend, albeit not statistically significant. These contrasting patterns in biomass change, despite the overall spatial stability of the barycentre, highlight the need for further investigation. To this end, we developed Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), following the methodology outlined in Section 4.2.1, using environmental outputs from nextGEMS (IFS-FESOM). This enables an evaluation of the added value of storm-resolving models in supporting ecosystem-based forecasting within upwelling systems.

4.2.3.2 Micronekton relative biomass

Here, we have also investigated how acoustic micronektonic density changed in response to key environmental drivers from 1995 to 2015. In this regard, we used acoustic sea surveys conducted in the sCCLME, complemented by environmental satellite data using the same approach as for *S. aurita* variables and fish schools (sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3.1). To obtain homogeneous data, only continental shelf data were considered (*i.e.*, 10–150 m). SSL micronekton were extracted using a threshold of -80 dB, meaning that SSLs with acoustic volume backscattering strengths (S_v in dB) below this threshold were excluded from the analysis. Environmental data include annual averages of SST and the Ekman transport index (Eke) from IFS-FESOM simulations, as well as SSC derived from an IFS-FESOM-based reconstruction. To estimate the influence of environmental variables on variations in micronekton density, generalised additive models (GAMs) were fitted. We used the nautical area scattering coefficient (NASC) as a proxy of micronekton relative density. The response variable in the model was the logarithmically transformed NASC. For the model selection procedure, different models were fitted using the REML method, and their performance was evaluated using key statistical measures, including adjusted R^2 , explained deviance, and Akaike information criterion (AIC). The final model was chosen based on its lowest AIC and highest explanatory power. For model validation, residual diagnostics were also performed to validate the model assumptions. Finally, based on the model that best fits our response variable (log-transformed NASC), we used projected environmental variables to generate future scenarios for changes in micronekton relative densities from 1995 to 2050. The final model was specified as follows:

$$\text{Log (NASC)} = \alpha + \text{s (SST, } k = 3) + \text{s (Eke, } k = 3) + \text{s (Chla, } k = 3) + \text{s (Year, } k = 3)$$

The final model showed a strong fit to the data, with predicted values closely aligning with observations (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Observed versus predicted micronekton relative density (NASC values) from the final Generalized Additive Model (GAM).

The final GAM explained 87% of the variance, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.70, indicating strong explanatory power. SSC emerged as the main explanatory variable ($p = 0.048$), suggesting a key role for primary productivity in determining the acoustic density of micronekton. Ekman transport SST had positive but non-significant effects ($p > 0.1$). Although the smoothed term for the year was not statistically significant ($p = 0.13$), it captured the interannual variability of micronekton biomass.

Using the GAM model, general trends in micronekton relative density were predicted for the period 1995–2015, serving as a basis for projections up to 2050 (Figure 28). The projection indicates a slight decline in micronekton biomass, consistent with the decrease in SSC levels in the CCLME (Behrenfeld *et al.*, 2006; Boyce *et al.*, 2010). SSC emerged as the main determining factor, supporting upward control. This trend reflects the predicted decline in small pelagic fish, suggesting that a decrease in SSC could limit prey availability. The wide confidence intervals reflect the model's uncertainty. These results highlight the system's vulnerability to declining productivity, which is consistent with global trends observed in upwelling ecosystems.

Figure 28. Predicted annual variation in relative micronektonic layers (SSL) biomass based on a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) using Ekman transport (E_{ke}), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), and Sea Surface chlorophyll- a (SSC) as environmental predictors from IFS-FESOM-derived datasets. Blue curve represents the observed acoustic-based total NASC (nautical area scattering coefficient). Red curve shows the predicted fish NASC density. The dashed red line represents the trend of predicted NASC, while the shaded red ribbon illustrates the 95% confidence interval of the predictions.

4.2.4 *Sardinella aurita*: biomass and northern shift trend

In section 2.2.2, we present the observation of a northern shift along 20-year time series of observations. Here, we investigate the projected impact of climate change on small pelagic fish in the sCCLME, studying the effect of climate change on the spatiotemporal dynamics of small pelagics, with a particular focus on *S. aurita* (Sarré *et al.*, 2024). Sardinellas are the most widely consumed pelagic species in West Africa (Ba *et al.*, 2022). For some time, fishermen have been drawing the attention of scientists to the impact of climate change on the distribution of fish species that are key to food security (Mbaye *et al.*, 2016, 2023; Brehmer *et al.*, 2018). However, any projection was specifically done for the area.

Figure 29: Southern CCLME, Shelf conditions (yellow) [100m bathy], and Offshore conditions (brown), better defined with 100 km off the shelf.

Our study area is depicted as extending from 12° to 28° N, encompassing the southern regions of Senegal and Morocco (Figure 29). The data we use are from two sources: the biological data from acoustics surveys (DFN), from 1995 to 2015; and environmental data [sea surface temperature (SST) from AVHRR, upwelling index (UW) from CCMP product, and SSC from SeaWifs/Modis]. Firstly, for the environmental variables, we look for seasonal patterns. To better explained the spatiotemporal dynamics of *S. aurita* biomass, we calculated seasonal averages for the upwelling season (November to May) and off-season (June to October) on the continental shelf (100 m of bathymetry) and along the offshore condition (better defined with 100 km off the shelf) (Figure 29) for the environmental parameters such as SST, and SSC and seasonal averages for the upwelling index (UW). In total, we have thirty-two sets (4x4x2) of three environmental parameters. We aim to determine which of these thirty-two sets of three parameters best adjust the interannual variability of our response variables, namely: relative abundance (*ABUN_AURITA*), Barycenter (*BAR_AURITA*), and *nTA*), and Northern limit (*NLIM_AURITA*) of *S. aurita*.

Secondly, we use a generalised additive model (Hastie *et al.*, 1987) to model the response variable (relative abundance, barycenter, northern limit of *S. aurita* (Sarré *et al.*, 2024)). To avoid overfitting due to a limited number of observations (n=10), we use a penalised spline and fix the number of knots to the strict minimum (k=3). The R software (version 4.4.1) has been used for modelling with some core packages, such as “mgcv” (Wood, 2017) and “gam.hp” (Lai and Tang, 2024). Our models are presented as follows, where we use a Gaussian distribution for the response variable and link identity functions for the explanatory variables, with cubic regression splines (*bs = cr*) for the standard smoothing parameter.

- Relative abundance of *S. aurita* model

$$ABUN_AURITA = \alpha + s(SSC, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(SST, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(UW, bs = cr, k = 3)$$

- Barycenter of *S. aurita* model

$$BAR_AURITA = \alpha + s(SSC, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(SST, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(UW, bs = cr, k = 3)$$

- Northern limit of *S. aurita* model

$$NLIM_AURITA = \alpha + s(SSC, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(SST, bs = cr, k = 3) + s(UW, bs = cr, k = 3)$$

Thirdly, based on the best-adjusted model for our response variables using the R-squared criterion, we utilise the predictions of SST and UW from IFS-FESOM and the IFS-FESOM-based SSC reconstruction to create a future scenario for the changes in biomass, barycentre, and northern limit of *S. aurita* in southern CCLME. The best scenario for each of our responses is the one that minimises the RMSE computed on the training period (1995-2015).

Figure 30 shows the change in *S. aurita* stock from 1995 to 2015. The difference in productivity between the north and south of Cap Blanc can be attributed to the seasonal nature of upwelling in these two sub-zones. Beyond 21°N, the upwelling is quasi-permanent, with a maximum during the summer but with less intensity than the southern upwelling, which occurs from November to May (Figure 30b). Obviously, SSC at the coast (isobath 100m) is richer during the upwelling season (Figure 30d).

Out of the thirty-two GAM models tested for each of the three responses, eighteen, eleven, and four models have a high percentage of adjusted R-squared with at least one significant environmental variable for biomass, barycentre, and the northern limit of *S. aurita*. Among the eighteen GAM models for the biomass of *S. aurita*, model number 16 exhibits the smallest RMSE, computed over the 20 years

(1995-2015), indicating that it best reproduces the observed biomass of *S. aurita*. Similarly, two models display the smallest RMSE for the barycentre and the northern limit, respectively.

Figure 30: Hovmoller representation of the spatio-temporal changes in the spatial distribution of (a) *Sardinella aurita* in the CCLME (12 to 30°N) from acoustic sea survey assessment of small pelagic from 1995 to 2015 (reproduced from Sarré et al., (2024)). Satellite climatology of environmental variables: (b) Upwelling Index, from 1988 to 2021; (c) Sea Surface Temperature, from 1982 to 2018; (d) Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a, from 1998 to 2007. “On-shore” is the area from the coast to the 100 m isobath. “Offshore” is the area between the 100 m isobath and 100 km offshore. The black horizontal line delimits the Cape Blanc limit (20°N). The red vertical line delimits the seasons: November to May is the cold season, and from June to October is the warm season.

Figure 30 shows the change in *S. aurita* stock from 1995 to 2015. The difference in productivity between the north and south of Cap Blanc can be attributed to the seasonal nature of upwelling in these two sub-zones. Beyond 21°N, the upwelling is quasi-permanent, with a maximum during the summer but with less intensity than the southern upwelling, which occurs from November to May (Figure 30b). Obviously, SSC at the coast (isobath 100m) is richer during the upwelling season (Figure 30d).

Out of the thirty-two GAM models tested for each of the three responses, eighteen, eleven, and four models have a high percentage of adjusted R-squared with at least one significant environmental variable for biomass, barycentre, and the northern limit of *S. aurita*. Among the eighteen GAM models for the biomass of *S. aurita*, model number 16 exhibits the smallest RMSE, computed over the 20 years (1995-2015), indicating that it best reproduces the observed biomass of *S. aurita*. Similarly, two models display the smallest RMSE for the barycentre and the northern limit, respectively.

The GAM for the biomass of *S. aurita*, using smoothed parameters such as SST, SSC, and UW, exhibits an explained deviance of 89.6%, accompanied by an adjusted R² of 0.815. SST has a significant negative linear effect on the biomass of *S. aurita* ($p < 0.05$), indicating that warmer SST have a decreasing impact on the fish stock. SST has a relative contribution of 12.5% to the explained deviance. Further, the UW shows a significant and non-linear effect (inverse U-shape) on the biomass of *S. aurita*. In other words, up to the threshold of $1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$, the upwelling intensity is favourable to the recruitment of the species, which implies the enhancement of the stock. However, above this threshold, the upwelling is unfavourable to recruitment. The upwelling index is the major driver, with 64.5% of the contribution. Although SSC has a 22.9% contribution, it appears to be non-significant. Consequently, the abundance of *S. aurita* along the spatial window of 12-28°N was primarily driven by physical parameters, such as SST and UW, rather than biological ones (SSC).

Based on the GAM result and IFS-FESOM environmental parameters, the prediction of *S. aurita* biomass over the historical period (1995-2015) has the smallest RMSE, indicating that it closely resembles the observed biomass of *S. aurita*. Over the prediction period (1995-2049), the *S. aurita* biomass (Figure 30a) exhibits a significant negative trend (p -value = 0.009), indicating a decrease in biomass. More specifically, we note a reduction of 126 tons per decade in the relative biomass of *S. aurita*. According to Sarré *et al.* (2024), the highly significant intensification of upwelling in the sCCLME, combined with the increase in SST due to warming, contributes to the decrease in the overall biomass of *S. aurita*. To this, we should not neglect the effect of the intensification of fishing efforts on the stock of the small pelagic fish (Diankha *et al.*, 2018; Baldé *et al.*, 2022).

The GAM result on the barycenter of *S. aurita* indicates that the explained deviance was 87.2% and the adjusted R^2 was 0.768. Contrary to the biomass fitting model, where SST and UW were significant, only the UW computed over the northern upwelling season is significant ($p < 0.05$). The fitted barycentre of *S. aurita* exhibits a significant linear relationship with the northward average upwelling computed over the warm season (UW_north). The fact that the upwelling in north CCLME, *i.e.*, above 20°N, is less intense than in the south implies that the northern upwelling is favourable to the recruitment of small pelagic. In other words, a less intense upwelling index favours the shift of the barycentre of *S. aurita*. Additionally, the northern UW index (UW_north) is the primary driver among the three parameters, accounting for nearly 61% of the contribution.

The prediction of the barycentre of *S. aurita* (Figure 31b) is made by using the GAM, which has the smallest RMSE. It can be seen that from 1995 to 2025, the predicted barycentre of *S. aurita* exhibits interannual fluctuations and relative stability around Cape Blanc (20°N). From 2025 to 2045, a significant and decreasing trend is expected for the barycentre of *S. aurita*. The displacement of the barycentre of *S. aurita* toward the south (below 20°N) appeared contrary to the northern extension using the north limit.

The GAM of the northern limit of *S. aurita*, using smoothed parameters such as SST, SSC, and UW, yields an explained deviance of 66.4% and an adjusted R^2 of 0.49. The physical parameters do not significantly influence the northern shift of *S. aurita*. SSC (in the northern upwelling, above 20°N) shows a significant and positive linear effect on the northern shift of *S. aurita*. The fact that, north of Cap Blanc, we have a quasi-permanent upwelling, bringing nutrient-rich water to the coastline, causes species in search of food to migrate north. The overall variability of the northern limit of *S. aurita* is driven by SSC, *i.e.*, 94% (p -value = 0.014).

Figure 31: Predicted a) relative biomass, b) barycentre, c) northern limit of *Sardinella aurita* based on Generalised Additive Model over twenty observational time series, using IFS-FESOM data (Sea Surface temperature and Wind) and Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a concentration (SSC) from IFS-FESOM-based SSC reconstruction. Blue curve is the acoustic observations done during the small pelagic assessment survey. Red curve is the biomass prediction. Light red shadow: Prediction confidence interval 95%.

The best scenario for predicting the northern limit of *S. aurita* (Figure 31c) reveals a significant and positive trend (p -value = 0.064) regarding the northern limit of *S. aurita*. Approximately, this

corresponds to a shift of 0.3° , *i.e.*, 33.6 km per decade. This finding aligns with previous results regarding the poleward shift of the populations of many marine species (Perry *et al.*, 2005; Cheung *et al.*, 2013; Sarré *et al.*, 2024).

4.2.5. Climate change in “Dakar Niño”

As introduced in Section 3, we have developed a deep learning method to reconstruct SSC using GLORYS physical variables and applied it to the IFS-FESOM model. In this section, we first investigate how well the DL approach can reproduce the marine ecosystem response to the Dakar Niño events in the applications of GLORYS and IFS-FESOM. Secondly, we will assess the future change in SST interannual variability in Northwest Africa.

Figure 32. Composite anomalies of Dakar Niño events for (a) Sea Surface Chlorophyll-*a* concentration (SSC) anomalies reconstructed from the GLORYS and (b) SSC anomalies applying to the IFS-FESOM. Results in (a) can be directly compared with the Figure 11b.

As shown in Figure 32, the DL algorithm can successfully capture the characteristic spatial pattern of chlorophyll-*a* response to the Dakar Niños, indicating that the selected physical variables are crucial to the SSC. However, the magnitude of the anomalies is more modest than that of the OC-CCI satellite data (Figure 11b). This may be because the training is performed using weekly GLORYS data, and some sharp variability is missing in the reconstructed outputs.

IFS-FESOM’s physical fields, to some extent, can reproduce the marine ecosystem behaviour under the Dakar Niño events (Figure 32b). Especially, the anomaly pattern off Senegal (12N and 16W-15W) is consistent with that of GLORYS’s reconstruction. However, the positive anomaly at higher latitudes is poorly represented in IFS-FESOM’s reconstruction. We will need to assess the physical variables of IFS-FESOM, such as vertical motion and ocean currents, to understand this misrepresentation of the marine ecosystem’s behaviour.

Figure 33. Time series of AMO index (bar) and SST standard deviation in running 21 years in the Dakar Index box (blue line, averaged over 9N-14N and 20W-17W) in March-April from 1990 to 2049 of the IFS-FESOM simulation (SSP3.70 scenario).

The IFS-FESOM climate change run indicates that the SST variability in the western African coast has a decreasing trend until 2039 (about 20% reduction). This result contradicts Koseki *et al.* (2024), indicating the potential amplification of Dakar Niño in future climate scenarios. Note that the climate change scenarios and focused periods differ between the two studies (Koseki *et al.*, 2024), which analysed the scenarios for RCP 8.5 and the period 2069-2099. After 2039, SST variability becomes stronger (Figure 33). This shift is consistent with the phase change of the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO) index from negative to positive. However, there is no clear relationship in the earlier period. Since Koseki *et al.* (2024) have not investigated the potential relationship between the AMO and Dakar Niño long-term variation, it will be necessary to gain more insights into how the AMO influences the Dakar Niño through longer-period simulations.

Figure 34: (a) Mar-Apr Dakar Index for GLORYS reanalysis (bar) and ICON-HAMOCC (line). (b) and (c) are the climatology and Dakar Niño composite anomalies of Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a concentration (SSC) in ICON-HAMOCC in March-April. The orange and blue dots in (a) denote the events of Dakar Niño and Niña in the ICON-HAMOCC run, respectively.

Similar to Section 2.3, we conducted a composite analysis for the SSC of the ICON-O/HAMOCC (Figure 34b and c). This is an atmospheric reanalysis forced ICON-O simulation that includes the HAMOCC biogeochemistry component (see Section 6 for more details). The ICON-O/HAMOCC exhibits a similar sawtooth pattern of SSC around Senegal: SSC is enhanced along the coast and reduced offshore, resulting in the confinement of SSC, which is quite similar to that of OC-CCI and UNnet reconstruction (Sections 2.3 and 4.2). This result is promising, and we will analyse the cause of this pattern of anomaly from a process-based perspective and with longer-term, integrated data.

We also investigated the inter-annual variability in the western African Coast impacts on SSC for the forced ICON-HAMOCC simulation (1996-2022). As Figure 34a shows, the ICON-HAMOCC reproduces the inter-annual variability of the Dakar Index (SST averaged over 9N-14N and 20W-17W) in line with GLORYS reanalysis. Using a threshold of 0.75 standard deviation of the Dakar Index (because of fewer), five warm and six cold events are identified from the time series. The ICON-HAMOCC captures most events identified in GLORYS, but a few events are missed, and the ICON-HAMOCC simulation captures different events.

6. ICON-O/HAMOCC: A Benchmark for SR-ESM biogeochemical validation

The available ICON-O simulations within nextGEMS had a temporally limited length (historical). They were thus less suitable than the IFS-FESOM (forecast) for addressing climate change impacts on marine productivity and fisheries. Therefore, they have not been used in this deliverable. We have, however,

benefited from forced ICON-Ocean model simulations coupled with biogeochemistry. These have enabled us to start addressing the importance of resolving sub-mesoscale processes for simulating primary productivity (Figure 35), particularly for the West African region. **This work has revealed that a realistic fine-scale spatial regional pattern emerges from the ICON-O/HAMOCC global simulation (10 km) within the complex sCCLME.** The ICON-O/HAMOCC simulations were kindly provided by Chegini Fatemeh and Tatiana Ilyina (Hamburg University, Germany) and were performed in the context of other projects⁵. During the nextGEMS hackathons (2023; supervised by Johann Jungclaus (MPIMET, Germany) and with initial support of his postdoc David M. Nielsen, followed by Chegini Fatemeh), we have investigated fine-scale spatial regional patterns within the sCCLME through a high-resolution (10 km) global simulation using the ICON-O/HAMOCC models (Figure 35). The surface wind used in this ICON-O/HAMOCC simulation is taken from the wind reanalysis and not from the nextGEMS atmospheric models (*i.e.*, of higher wind resolution). Nevertheless, it surprisingly well reproduces the interannual variability of the SSC (Figure 36b). The interest here is to challenge the use of global oceanographic models that allow for reproducing fine-scale regional spatial structures. The results display fine-scale spatial patterns within the sCCLME, as simulated by ICON-O/HAMOCC, along with a comparison to satellite observations (Figure 36a).

Figure 35: The Sea surface chlorophyll-a concentration in the Western Africa upwelling-fisheries system (the south part of the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem) as reproduced from the ICON/HAMOCC coupled model vs satellite observations (1996-2012 for SST and 1998-2012 for Chl-a). ICON: Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic Model (10 km). HAMOCC: HAMBURG Ocean Carbon Cycle global biogeochemistry model.

Figure 36: Comparison of the SSC for the West-African upwelling system (10 °N – 33 °N) between a Phytoplankton biomass index from the ICON/HAMOCC model (red line) and a combined Chl-a product from SeaWiFS and MODIS data from 1998 to 2022, for (a) the seasonal monthly signal and (b) the yearly averages. The correlation between both time series (Spearman coefficient) is 0.61. The light green line (SW R2022) is the SeaWiFS Chl-a, and the dark green line (MO corr.) is the adjusted MODIS Chl-a. For comparison, the green dotted line (MO) represents the MODIS data before adjustment.

⁵ ESM2025: Funded by EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement 101003536: project ESM2025–Earth System Models for the Future. And CLICCS: DFG Funded under Germany’s Excellence Strategy –EXC 2037 ‘CLICCS - Climate, Climatic Change, and Society’ – Project Number: 390683824

This work provides a valuable perspective for the realistic representation of fine-scale spatial regional patterns within a global simulation. It highlights the importance of such models for understanding and managing complex coastal ecosystems (as East Border Upwelling System, “EBUS”). It also represents an interesting avenue for further work on D7.3 within the framework of nextGEMS, particularly in terms of its importance for West African fisheries.

7. Deviation

We were not able to provide reconstructions of SSC for the global ocean at a fine scale because of limitations in our ML approach. Nevertheless, our results, based on 0.25-degree reconstructions of weekly data, have revealed interesting findings. Furthermore, we have utilised forced (ERA5) ocean model simulations, ICON/HAMOCC with interactive biogeochemistry, to assess the impacts of sub-mesoscale processes on SSC (Sec. 4).

8. Conclusion

Remote sensing, particularly the combined use of satellite ocean colour data and fisheries acoustics, has proven essential for monitoring sub-regional marine ecosystems. These tools enable continuous, large-scale observation of key indicators, such as sea surface chlorophyll-*a* concentration (SSC), small pelagic fish stocks, fish schools and micronektonic biomasses, offering critical baselines for detecting ecological shifts in data-poor and climate-vulnerable regions. Our analysis confirms that climate change is already affecting the West African marine ecosystem, with observed trends including altered upwelling dynamics, shifting isotherms, and a documented northward redistribution of key species such as *S. aurita*. These changes highlight the integration of high-resolution observations and modelling approaches to support adaptive fisheries management and long-term sustainability.

Given the influence of environmental variables on the spatial distribution and biomass of micronekton (as prey) and small pelagic fish, we developed forecasting tools based on Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), first calibrated using a 20-year time series of observational data. Subsequently, we applied the nextGEMS outputs (IFS-FESOM) to project changes through to 2050. As nextGEMS does not directly provide SSC, we introduced a novel deep learning approach to reconstruct SSC from physical variables using Glorys for the learning phase and IFS-FESOM for the reconstruction. However, the rebuilding of SSC at sub-seasonal scales remains limited, particularly in dynamic systems such as Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems (EBUS), which are found in north-west Africa. Here, fine-scale physical processes and trophic interactions introduce significant modelling uncertainties. These limitations must be carefully considered when using model outputs to inform fisheries management in these regions.

Despite these challenges, nextGEMS (IFS-FESOM) outperforms CMIP6 models in resolving fine-scale ocean–atmosphere interactions in coastal and upwelling zones, including SST fronts and mesoscale dynamics critical for ecosystem productivity, particularly in the Senegal–Mauritania Frontal Zone. Furthermore, nextGEMS successfully reproduces regional climate extremes such as Dakar Niño/Niña events and their localised impacts on marine productivity, which are poorly represented in CMIP6 models due to their coarser resolution and simplified physics.

At the global scale, projections from both nextGEMS and CMIP6 suggest, with poor confidence, that SSC will show little to no consistent trend by mid-century. While CMIP6 models display a wide range of outcomes) from moderate increases to notable declines (the overall ensemble points to negligible change. Similarly, the SSC reconstruction from IFS-FESOM indicates a weak long-term trend and limited interannual variability. Yet, the absence of common spatial patterns of SSC trends between CMIP6 models and IFS-FESOM should raise concerns about the robustness of any future projections (either from CMIP6 or from IFS-FESOM). However, nextGEMS captures finer-scale spatial features near coasts and frontal zones that low-resolution CMIP6 models cannot simulate, underscoring the importance of regional-scale analyses in detecting ecologically significant shifts.

A drawback of the nextGEMS simulations is that they do not incorporate an interactive biogeochemistry module. To overcome this, we have developed an innovative AI approach that is

trained to make observations to use model physical parameters to emulate SSC. This approach shows promise for bridging the gap between physics and biology in current storm-resolving models, but it does suppress variability. Our comparison with ICON-O/HAMOCC simulations shows good agreement with satellite observations of SSC, particularly in terms of evolution and fine-scale structure. It will be useful to see further development of these models, which can also provide data for training AI approaches.

Despite observed northward shifts in *S. aurita* distribution in recent decades—driven by changes in SST, upwelling, and SSC—our nextGEMS forecasts to 2050 suggest no continued northward movement (barycentre) but rather a relative stability. This divergence indicates that retrospective 26-year trends may have limited value for projecting future dynamics under changing climate conditions, or they must be considered with caution due to their limited temporal representativeness. Nevertheless, the northern limit of *S. aurita* shows a continued extension to the north, that is to say, a northern expansion of the species distribution area. Lastly, considering the high uncertainty in our simulations, the biomass of *S. aurita* is expected to show a step-down by 2050, corresponding to a low decrease in micronektonic biomass. A surprising result from the IFS-FESOM simulation was the significant decrease in the relative biomass of small pelagic fish schools. This result may be biased due to the absence of species allocation in all acoustic data analysis in Northwest Africa and the need to consider an ecosystemic approach more effectively. Nonetheless, nextGEMS modelling efforts based on fish school acoustic data and micronektonic biomass and spatial structure offer promising pathways for capturing ecological responses to environmental variability, especially in the absence of detailed species-level data.

However, the current level of uncertainty in SSC, an essential variable for fisheries analysis, limits the reliability of nextGEMS forecasts on West African marine productivity at this stage. Any significant shift in the distribution of *S. aurita* or other small pelagic stocks could have major socio-economic implications. In Mauritania and southern Morocco, fisheries make a substantial contribution to national GDP, while in Senegal, they remain a key source of protein and employment. Recent pressures from fishmeal factories and semi-industrial vessels have exacerbated overexploitation, particularly on *S. aurita* (FAO, 2023). As concerns rise across national research institutions, there is a clear need to establish a harmonised, transboundary monitoring system for shared fish stocks and to deepen research on the impacts of climate change on fisheries. Despite uncertainties, this work lays the groundwork for several future analyses and early warning systems. It will be particularly relevant to anticipate future changes in the Northwest African marine ecosystem, thereby preventing future conflicts over fisheries resources and informing adaptation strategies from national authorities on food security.

9. References

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